

ABOUT SYNONYMIC SENTENCES IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Linguistics

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Abstract

The article deals with syntactic synonymy, in the resolution of which the opinions of scientists are still varied. Each language is different and rich in its own way. He owes this diversity and wealth to a stock of synonyms, synonymous words, sentences. Synonyms come in both simple and complex sentences.

Grammatical synonyms in Russian linguistics began to be studied in the XVIII-XIX centuries. Scientists M.V.Lomonosov, A.Kh.Vostokov, F.I.Buslaev, K.S.Aksakova, A.A.Shakhmatov, A.Bulakhovskiy studying the works of A.Pushkin, V.A.Zhukovsky, I.S.Turgenev noted the presence of grammatical variants in them.

M.V. Lomonosov was the first to point out the existence of grammatical parallels, and A. M. Peshkovskiy first used the term “synonym” and divided grammatical synonyms into morphological and syntactic ones.

Following A.M.Peshkovskiy, the syntactic synonyms became the object of study of G.I. Rakhter, M.K.Milykh, I.I.Kovtunova, L.Maksimov, V.I.Kononenko and many others.

In resolving the issue of syntactic synonymy, the opinions of scientists are still diverse. Some rely on the heterogeneity of content, the difference in structure (V.I.Kononenko, L.Graudin), on differences only in shades of meaning (A.N.Gvozdev), on designs with identical independent words, constructions with similar lexical elements, but Different in structure (L.Maksimov). And according to I.I.Kovtunova, “syntactic synonyms should be considered constructions that represent complete grammatical parallelism...”. By M.M.Ignatyev unions, prepositions, word forms consider the main signs of the difference between syntactic synonymy and synonymy of lexical and morphological, but M.F.Palevskaya denies this opinion. E.I.Shchendels is a supporter of the single-structural grammatical synonyms. O.S.Akhmanova, A.I.Uemov, F.G.Farber are considered this phenomenon not only as a linguistic synonymy, but also as essentially logical. In our opinion, synonyms are not only lexical, but syntactic. Synonyms should be explored from both a practical and a general theoretical point of view, since all phenomena date back to the philosophical and pragmatic nature of language.¹

¹ Safarov, SH. Pragmalingvistika. –T., 2008.

As can be seen from the sources of opinion, scientists are not divided even when singling out such principles of syntactic synonymy as “general grammatical meaning”, “difference”, “difference in stylistic nuances”. But according to the principle of “interchangeability” their opinions do not coincide. According to V.P.Sukhotin, interchangeability is one of the important features of syntactic synonymy.² This opinion of V.P.Sukhotin is supported by A.N.Gvozdev, A.P.Zaitsev, M.M.Ignatyev, and others.

In linguistics, especially, in Uzbek, a lot of works on lexical synonymy, but grammatical and stylistic synonymy, except for the read works, was studied in passing.

The question of synonymy as a manifestation of semantic-systemic relations was considered in the works of S.D.Katsnelson (1965), O.Akhmanova (1957), E.Mednikov (1974), A.Ufimtsev (1967), V.G.Pak (1977), D.N.Shmelev (1977), N.Bradle (1998), D.R.Dowty (2004), M.Furberg (2002), R.M.Rempson (2001).

In Uzbek linguistics, this problem was studied more thoroughly by R.R.Sayfullaeva and Zh.Sh. Djumabaeva.³ Further, let us dwell on some points of syntactic synonymy, in particular the synonymy of sentences. In synonymic relations can come as suggestions in general, and members of the proposal. In such cases, one of the members of the proposal, expressing the content of one or more sentences, may enter into a synonymous relationship with the proposal.

Therefore, one term can mean a complex mean. This, basically, looks like this: —*Мен ўз взводим биланқоламан. Сиз ротаниолибкетинг, дебоёқтираб, қаттиқтуруиболди,— Ўртоқ Отаев ҳамқолмоқчи. Лекин мен буни овозга қўймоқчи эмасман. Ўзим қоламан (Шухрат) (I'll stay with my platoon. You will lead the company, "he said firmly." Comrade Atayev also wants to stay. " But I do not want to put it to the vote).* The member of the “buni” proposal in this context expresses the content of the proposals:

Мен ўз взводим биланқоламан. Сиз ротаниолибкетинг. Ўртоқ Отаев ҳамқолмоқчи.

Parts of a sentence can be synonymous with both simple and complex sentences.

Part of the proposal is a simple sentence:

1) *Улар сусткорлик қиляпти. Буменга ёқмайди (from Newspaper) (They linger. I do not like it);*

2) *Сенга бойлик керак эмас. Буни биламан. (А.Якубов). (You do not need wealth. I know this);*

3) *Уҳеч дарс қолдирмайди, аъло ўқийди, оммавий ишларга ҳам амактив қатнашади. Шуту файли уни мактаб коллективия хишқўради (из газеты) (He does not miss classes, he studies well, actively participates in public work. Thanks to this, the school team loves it).*

² Sukhotin V.P. Sintaksicheskaya sinonimiya v sovremennom russkom literaturnom yazyke. M. 1970.

³ Sayfullaeva R.R. Sinonimiya prostyx povestvovatelnykh predlozeniy v sovremennom uzbekskom yazyke. T., 1991. Djumabaeva J.SH. Turlitizimlillarda leksikvastilistik graduaionimiya. T., 2017.

In the first sentence in the above examples, the subject “bu” expresses the content of the simple sentence *Ularsustkorliqilyapti* (They linger), in the second, this role is performed by the addition of “buni”, i.e. expresses the content of a simple sentence *Sengaboylikkerakemas* (You do not need wealth).

When translating these sentences into Russian, the members of the sentence “Bu” and “Buni” also express the meanings of previous simple sentences. Both words *bu* and *buni* are presented like this:

- a) *I do not like this.*
- b) *It is (this) I know.*

In the case of the use of these words in the composition of the other two, that is, the previous ones, we obtain the following constructions, namely:

- a) *I do not like the fact that they are slow.*
- b) *I know that you do not need wealth.*

Here the author uses words to replace them and avoid repetition. And in the opposite case, they are transformed into complex sentences.

A sentence part is a complex sentence:

Ора яқин, атроф яланглик, кейин душманлар ҳам мени отиб олмагунча куймас эди. Шунини ўйлаб, ўзимни босдим-да, снайпер бекиниб ётган жойни кузатиб ётавердим (П. Кадыров) (*The distance is close, the terrain is open, and then the enemies would not rest until they shot me. After thinking about this, I restrained myself, began to lie down to watch the place where the sniper was hiding*). The member of the *shuni* sentence in this case expresses the importance of a complex sentence consisting of three components: a) *orayaqin*; b) *atrofyalangi*; c) *dushmanlar ham meniotibolmaguncha qo'ymasedi*.

1) part of the sentence – a compound sentence *Ўрта мактабни битириб чиққан йигит-қизларнинг кўпчилиги «физика», «математика» фанларини яхши билмайдилар, ва уларнинг «она тили»дан саводходликлари ҳам анча паст. Бу халқ маорифи ходимларини анча ташвишга солмоқда* (Many young men and girls who graduated from high school have a poor knowledge of physics, mathematics and knowledge of their native language are also low.) This is very much of concern to educators);

2) the sentence part is a complex sentence: *Ҳаво совуқ бўлса ҳам, у келади.*

Мен бунга ишонамаи («Муштум») (Although the weather is cold, it will come, I'm sure of it);

3) the member of the proposal is an alliance proposal:

Билмасанг, билиб қўй: бизнинг план Гитлер қўлини кўтарган кунни тўлади. Шундай деб ёз (Шухрат) (If you do not know, then keep in mind: our plan will be executed when Hitler gives in. So write).

The sentence part, which is synonymous with the whole sentence, is usually expressed by a pronoun. Of all the varieties of pronouns, most often in this role are the demonstrative pronouns. This includes pronouns of the type *u, bu, o'sha, ana, mana, ana o'sha, manashu, manabu, anashu*, etc.

These pronouns can take the form of a nominative, parent, dative, local, source cases; can be used with postpositions such *asbilan, uchun, tufayli, kabi, singari* and relative words *maqсад, umid, niyat, harakat, natija, oqibat, sabab*.

To the demonstrative pronouns can be added affixes-postpositions *-day, -dek*, equal in terms of postpositions *kabi, singari, go'yo and shunday, shuningdek*. They serve to express the content of the sentence.

With the synonymity of the sentence member with the named words with suggestions, two provisions are observed:

1) the components of a complex sentence are synonymous with one of its members:

Ҳукуматимизнинг яна бир хусусияти шундаки, халқ манфаатлари учун фақат ўзи курашибгина қолмай, кенг меҳнаткашлар оммасини курашга отлантириб, ўзига эргаштириб бора олади ҳам. (One of the peculiarities of our government is that for the good of the people it fights not only itself, it directs broad masses of working people to this struggle and leads them along). This two-component complex proposition and the part of the first component *shuki* sentence express the content of the second component;

2) one of the parts of an independent proposal that is not part of the complex, expresses the content of the preceding sentence and is used as its synonym:

Бунинг ҳаммаси ҳаёт-мамот урушида бизга галаба келтирган улуг туйғулардан эканига ҳам унинг энди ақли етмоқда эди. Шунинг учун онасининг қалбидаги илинжни энди асраб-авайлагиси келди. (П.Кадыров). (Only now he

began to understand all the feelings that brought us victory in the war for life, so he wanted to cherish the hope of the mother's heart).

The synonymy of one part of the sentence and the sentence as a whole is quantitatively diverse. Here one of the members can express the content of one or more sentences:

1) the sentence part is synonymous with one sentence: ...*Унча- мунча ваъз айтишни хам билиш керак бўлади. Бусиз иш битмайди.* (А.Каххар) (To some extent it is necessary and able to make a speech. *Хатто бир гал Мурзинга шама ҳам қилган эди. Шунда Мурзин алланечук бўлиб кетиб: кун ҳам, ой ҳам унга туққан, —деди.* (Шухрат) (One day he even hinted at Murzin, then Murzin was feeling uneasy, said: everything should be in her favor);

2) the sentence member is synonymous with two sentences: *Ейилган овқат яхши ҳазм ва ош бўлиши учун организмга кислород узлуксиз ўтиб туриши лозим. Мия тўқимаси, хусусан, кислород етишмаслигига жуда сезгирдир. Ақлий меҳнат аҳллари бунга эрдан чиқармасликлари керак* (Календарь) (To ensure that the consumed food is digested, digested, the body needs oxygen supply. The brain nerves are very sensitive to lack of oxygen.) Science people should not forget about this);

– *Уни нима деб аташимиздан катъий назар, пулга сотилмай- диган одам йуқ, пул тўплансин!* —деди мерганлардан дўриллаган бир овозли биттаси.

Халқ яна шовқин кўтарди (*people rustled again*):

– *Тўплансин!* (*Collect!*).

– *Эрназардан пулимизни аямаймиз* (*We will not spare money for the sake of Ernazar*).

– *Маъқул гап бу* (It is right). (*“Шарқ юлдузи.*)

In this example, the predicate pronounced бу the pronoun is synonymous with the two preceding sentences тўплансини Эрназардан пулимизни аямаймиз;

3) the sentence part is a synonym of the three sentences: *У ҳеч дарс қолдирмайди. Аъло ўқийди. Оммавий ишларга ҳам фаол қатнашади. Шу туфайли уни мактаб жамоаси яхши кўради.* (from Newspaper) – *He never misses classes. Excellent studying. Actively participates in public work. Thanks to this, the collective of the school loves it.*

The part of the sentence shutufayli of the fourth example expresses the meaning of the three ahead proposals. In the last sentence, its part thanks to this expresses the cause of the love of the collective. And the use of each sentence separately shows the reasons, and affirms their credibility:

4) the sentence part is synonymous with the four sentences.

–*Йўқ, бу қўрқоқлик эмас, мардлиқ. Қўрқоқ одам довдираб, ўзини йўқотади. Сиз йўқотмадингиз! Бундай чоғда ақл кишидан тамоман бегона бўлиб қолади.* (Я.Шукуров) - *No, it's not cowardice. Courage. A cowardly man would be puzzled. At such a time a person loses his mind.*

In this example, the writer presents the idea presented in these four sentences by the last letter of the *Бундай чоғда ақл кишидан тамоман бегона бўлиб қолади*. And it is here that the circumstance of time is used - one of the members of the proposal *–Бундай чоғда* (*At such a time // moment // ...*) acts as a synonym, where the author very briefly summarizes his thought in a completely different form.

Parts of a sentence can be synonymous with five, six, seven or more sentences, as well as large texts. Here is one of the texts: *Келинчак янги тушган оиласида аввал деярли ё умуман бўлмаган. Бу хонадоннинг ўзига хос хусусияти бор. Эҳтимол, катта-ю кичик бор қозондан ош ичар. Эҳтимол, «Хайр, ойижон!» демай, ҳеч ким кўчага — ишга ё ўқишга кетмас. Она ҳам «яхши бориб кел» демаса, кўнгли ўрнига тушмас. Балки келинлар қайноналари билан шундай аҳилларки, эрларига айтолмаган сирларини унга айтишар. Келин эса, турмушга чиққунча бошқа оилада, шароитда тарбия кўрган. Ким билади дейсиз, менинг давримда ўйнаб олишсин, деб, ойиси уни меҳнатга солмагандир ё али деса бали дейдиган қилиб ўстиргандир. Хуллас, бунга дастур йўқ.* (Я. Саъдуллаева) (*The family, where she came, the daughter-in-law did not know at all and was not in her. This family has its own characteristics. The older and younger are probably cooked in the same boiler. Probably none of them, without saying “Goodbye, Mummy”, does not go out into the street to work or study. Maybe the mother's heart will not rest until she tells her children “Happy”. Maybe in this family the daughter-in-law is so friendly with the mother-in-law that some of her secrets speak not to her husbands, but her mother-in-law. A daughter in law, until she got married, was brought up in another situation. Who knows, maybe her mother did not teach her to work, she caressed her too much, cherished her, made her sharp on her tongue. In general, there is no guidance here).*

Bunga in the sentence of *Хуллас, бунга дастур йўқ*, expresses the content of the above text.

There are cases when in the sentence one or two of its parts, consistently explaining a phenomenon in another sentence, to which one of them is synonymously, is a synonym and the second part of the explained sentence. For example:

Кези келганда, шуни айтиш керакки, айрим кишилар, дам олиш деганда, соя-салқин жойларда яхши овқатланиб, мириқиб ухлашни тушунади. Афсуски, бунинчаинакам хордиқ чиқариш деб бўлмайди, аксинча, бу ҳол узоқ давом этса, соғлиққа зиён келтириши турган гап. («Фан ва турмуш»)(It should be said that some people have a good rest and a good meal under the shade of the trees, but unfortunately, it can not be called a rest, because if it lasts a long time, it can damage health).

The part of the sentence of the *shuni* of this example expresses the contents of the sentences of *Айрим кишилар, дам олиш деганда, соя-салқин жойларда яхши овқатланиб, мириқиб ухлашни тушунади*, the parts of the sentence *buni* and *bu* also express the content of the same sentence.

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